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A CASE REPORT OF RARE HYPERFUNCTIONING METASTATIC THYROID CARCINOMA

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Introduction: Thyrotoxicosis due to functioning metastases from differentiated thyroid cancer (DTC) is rare. The diagnosis is usually made after other causes of thyrotoxicosis have been ruled out, such as toxic adenoma or Graves' disease. **Case report:** We present a case of a 67-year-old patient who had been treated for hyperthyroidism caused by a toxic adenoma, but failed to achieve a euthyroid state after two doses of radioactive iodine therapy (RIT). During this time, the patient developed pelvic pain and weight loss and was referred for an FDG PET/CT examination which revealed a soft tissue lesion in the sacrum and multiple metastases in the bones. The subsequent biopsy of the sacral mass revealed that the tumor was a metastasis from a DTC. The patient further received palliative radiotherapy treatment for the sacrum change followed by total thyroidectomy (TT) two months later. Eight weeks after TT the patient had a toxic recurrence and she was referred to an I-131 whole-body scan (WBS). The WBS showed multiple lung and bone metastases with intense iodine accumulation. On the basis of these findings, she was administered with two cycles of high-dose RIT. After RIT, the patient had stable disease for a year and then underwent Gamma Knife treatment for brain metastases. The patient is currently on Sorafenib treatment and remains stable. **Conclusion:** This case emphasizes that thyrotoxicosis should be considered as a potential complication of metastatic disease, in which both diagnostic and therapeutic application of radioiodine can play a significant role.

Keywords: Hyperfunctioning metastasis, differentiated thyroid cancer, thyrotoxicosis